

Error in Data Filtering and loose cable on the Ground Node

A Brief Technical Report

Emmanuel Kondela

Mary Nsabagwa

Maximus Byamukama

1. Background

Due to the previous movement of the weather station from the store, a few changes were made. One of the changes was restoring the report mask of the ground node. During the change of the report mask, the soil moisture reading (V_A1) was dropped from the report mask. The problem caused the data filtering software (seltag) to return errors during the formatting resulting into failure to update the real time plots.

After restoring the report mask, it was observed that the moisture sensor recorded 0.0, a value that was not expected. Although we earlier thought that the sensor was damaged, we discovered that there was a loose connection between the sensor and the RS2-mote's ADC1 connection.

2. Activities on troubleshooting the reports

On the 28th September 2015, the plots for the ground node were displaying old dates ending on 24th September 2015. Below are the steps we took to identify and rectify the problem

No	Activity	Reason	Result
1	Checking the report mask of the ground node both via the mobile application and SSH	To establish that the report mask from the ground node is showing the right dates	Date was up to date
2	Checking plots.html	Establish which png file name giving wrong results	Sensors/gndplot.png
3	Checking the last modification date of the gndplot.png	To establish if the program still had rights to modify the file	The image file was new meaning gnu plot is writing to the image file in real time
4	Checking the cron tab	To find out which files are called by the cron jobs in order to edit the png graph file	/usr/local/scripts/sensor splot.sh
5	Checking sens.sh	To find out the commands that generate the graph	A command extracting data from sensors.dat contains a parameter V_A1 which no longer

			exists in sensors.dat
6	Checking sensors.dat for any instance of V_A1 in its previous records	To establish if the parameter has ever been recorded	V_A1 was last recorded on 24 th September 2015 at 10:43:25 am
7	Adding the V_A1 parameter to the report mask	To enable addition of V_A1 to the sensors.dat file	Plots working perfectly

3. Recommendations

- Seltag should give informative error messages. Currently, if the command has errors, no output is returned
- Robust connections and longer cables are required
- Since “V_A1= Voltage Analog 1 (A1) (F)”, a description of the parameter given on the sensd website does not correspond to meteorological parameter, a document explaining what sensors are connected to the mote be written to make troubleshooting much more easier.

Appendix

```

### Plot data from sensor node gnd (outdoor) if present
#filter $1 $2
if [ gnd == $1 ]; then
echo gnd
tail -n2 $DATA | grep $1 | grep ^20 | /usr/sbin/seltag -sel T=%s T1=%s V_HC=%s V_IN=%s V_A1=%s RSSI=%s | grep -v Miss > $TMP
wc -l /tmp/sens.dat
if [ gndplot.png == $3 ]; then
echo gndplot
PLOT=/usr/local/scripts/gnd.gp
plot $3
elif [ gndPowerplot.png == $3 ]; then
echo gndPowerplot
PLOT=/usr/local/scripts/gndPower.gp
plot $3
fi
fi

```

Figure 1: Data extraction of sens.sh showing line 5 attempting to pick V_A1 value which was not in sensors.dat file

Figure 2: Graph generated after removal of V_A1 (soil moisture reading) from the seltag command

Figure 3: Graph generated after restoration of V_A1 (soil moisture reading) in the seltag command and restoration of V_A1 ground node in the report mask

Figure 4: Ground Node showing loose connection of the moisture sensor